

Intrusion Detection System for Vehicular ad Hoc Network Attacks

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Abstract

The Vehicular ad-hoc Network (VANET) is a new subcategory of Mobile ad-hoc Networks that has excellent potential application in intelligent transportation systems. The cyberattack on vehicles will lead to privacy leaks and financial losses and could even become a national public safety issue. In this paper, a multi-level Intrusion Detection System based on machine learning algorithms is developed in order to detect multiple types of attacks on VANET. The proposed model combined two feature selection techniques and four tree-based algorithms for classification. performance Moreover, the model is evaluated using CICIDS 2017 dataset. Experiment results show that the proposed model achieves 99.86% attack detection accuracy. The experimental findings on the vehicular network demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed solution and the ability to implement it in real-time environments.

Keywords: Autonomous vehicles, Intrusion detection systems, Machine learning, Cybersecurity, VANET.

1. Introduction

The evolution in Information Communications Technology (ICT) and networks has accelerated Intelligent transportation systems (ITS) applications. With the application of information and communication technologies such as Internet of Things (IoT), intelligent sensors, artificial intelligence (AI), big data, cloud computing, and 5G networks, the new generation of automotive systems and assisted driving technologies are rapidly improving. However, when modern communication technologies bring easy connection with convenience to users, they also bring increasingly severe cybersecurity threats to the transportation network and smart city (Ma, 2021). In recent years, and with the vast data availability, the increase in information security needs has attracted significant attention from researchers. Electric Vehicles (EV) and Autonomous Vehicles (AV) have the characteristics of close integration of network information and physical components (Liang et al., 2018). Therefore,

attacks on the ITS network will not only cause privacy leakage and economic losses but also endanger human life and even become a national public safety issue.

The new generation of automotive systems relies on two networks type: in-vehicle networks and external networks, which allow the EVs sharing communication bandwidth, storage, and computing resources to realize the collaborative processing of a large amount of real-time data. The development of ITS is a double-edged sword for both the external vehicle network and the in-vehicle network, which faces new problems and challenges. However, the current automotive network environment is full of issues and challenges in information security aspects. These challenges mainly include an open external environment (multiple ways of wireless access), limited resources (bandwidth resources, computing power, and energy, storage resources and cache, etc.), strict time requirements (real-time and schedulable analysis), and cost sensitivity brought by large-scale applications. Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) technologies connect vehicles to the exterior world via external networks. Modern vehicles can communicate with other vehicles in different ways, such as vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-roadside infrastructure (V2I) thanks to vehicle to everything V2X technology (Al-Jarrah et al., 2019). The ad-hoc mobile communication technology applied to vehicular network applications and introduced as vehicular ad hoc network (VANET). Generally, researchers and industry agree that VANET holds great potential for implementing ITS, which would simultaneously improve safety and dependability on our increasingly crowded highways (Eze et al., 2014). The communication medium in EV and AV is VANET, which comprises ad hoc infrastructure and mobile vehicles communicating via open wireless channels. Shared wireless medium, high mobility, and lack of centralized security services make VANET more susceptible to attacks. Using machine learning (ML) and data analytics in intrusion detection system (IDS) model development can spot network threats is widely considered a new promising area in cybersecurity (Injadat et al., 2021). However, the current detection techniques have much-limited prevention as these techniques designed for a set of known attacks, which is difficult to avoid the recent attacks designed to penetrate existing security systems. Therefore, the need for IDS has increased to protect V2X communication EV and AV from potential and updated attacks (El-Rewini et al., 2020).

Some authentication methods, such as the Intrusion Presentation System (IPS), detect unauthorized users and prevent them from accessing the network (Giannopoulos et al., 2017). However, an IPS can be bypassed by a skillful intrusion. Therefore, an IDS can be the second layer of security to detect these types of intrusions. The role of an IDS is to continuously monitor network

activity and collect relevant data for further analysis to make appropriate decisions in different situations.

Due to the growth of knowledge and technology, the problem of decision-making is becoming more complicated to be handled; thus, developing new techniques to solve it is critical. Classifier combination in IDS is a promising direction in ML techniques. Today's main challenge in massively connected networks, including VANET, is keeping valuable information away from intruders and hackers. Despite these threats, the developers of IDS make every effort to combat cyber-attacks. There are two types of IDS: misuse and anomaly detections. Misuse detection aims to detect instances of network intrusions by comparing current activities to an intruder's expected actions (Bangui H et al. 2022). In anomaly detection, the typical traffic flow over a network is first established by the system administrator; any deviation from this baseline or pattern that does not match an expected normal state will be considered an anomaly (Baharlouei et al., 2022). IDS is installed inside network gateways to monitor the traffic on the external network (Larson et al., 2008). Suspicious network activity is detected when abnormal traffic passes through gateways in external vehicular networks. Then any packet transmitted in the VANET is collected by network packet taps and examined by the developed IDS before passing to the connected vehicle (Zhou et al., 2018). Traditional networks have utilized IDS-based techniques for years because they efficiently deal with network attacks. However, fundamental features of these networks, such as restriction in power supply, node storage, poor transmission range, and processing capacity (Fu et al., 2016) provide significant challenges to deploying IDS-based systems in highly mobile and delay-sensitive networks such as VANET. Due to these restrictions, classic IDS and other security solutions for wired/wireless networks cannot apply to VANETs (Sharma & Kaul, 2018). VANET has distinct characteristics that must be dealt with and considered during IDSs development. The most important of these characteristics is the high mobility in the network, and the new protocols used in connecting VANET networks (Indira & Joy, 1015) since the constant movement in the mobility makes monitoring intrusions difficult, affecting the detection of malicious attacks. On the other hand, VANET does not use traditional network protocols but deals with new and special protocols, such as 802.11p and Dedicated Short-Range Communication (Kenney, 2011), as well as 5G communications. With the development of communications protocols and the increasing sources of attacks, tremendous types of intrusions and attacks target VANET network. Therefore, developing an IDS for the VANET network requires special considerations to enhance the network's security and detect the new generation of attacks in time.

This paper focuses on the information security threats VANET encountered in developing intelligent connected vehicles. In the related literature, many ML techniques are used in the classification stage, either individually or collectively. Feature Selection (FS) techniques are used to select the features that help get better results. Despite this, some ML techniques need considerable resources to give the desired results. Most of the current research used one type of FS method, either filter, wrapper, or embedded methods, which allow the model to select certain features that may not affect the results or are redundant.

To preserve the effort that the model requires in literature and achieve better results, we adopt ML techniques from the same category, i.e., Decision Tree (DT)-based models. We also use the hybrid FS method (Filter and Embedded methods) to assist the model in selecting relevant and significant features from the dataset without duplicating data. More precisely, in the IDS model, we propose a feature engineering model based on Random Forest (RF) (Breiman, 2001) and Fast Correlation-Based Filter (Yu & Liu, 2003) to reduce the dataset dimensionality and select the best features that enhance the detection rate and model accuracy. After feature engineering, we implement four ML models, each consisting of tree-based algorithms to detect unpredicted attacks and achieve precise results with higher accuracy and considering the alarming rate. The proposed tree-based algorithms are extreme gradient boosting decision tree (XGBoost) (Chen et al., 2015), RF, DT, and ExtraTrees (EXT) Classifiers (Geurts, P et al., 2006). The model is evaluated on the CICIDS2017 benchmark (Sharafaldin et al., 2018), considering parameters such as packet delivery, dropped and delays, and network latency. To improve the performance of the proposed model, we used the stacking method. Stacking is a common ensemble learning strategy that involves using each algorithm's output labels as input to train a robust stack model, which is then responsible for making the final prediction (Snoek et al., 2012). In particular, we use synergically DT-based models for the following reasons: 1) DT-based models can work effectively with complex and non-linear data; 2) using this kind of parallel ensemble model allows improving efficiency and reducing training time; 3) DT-based models work randomly while constructing the model, and that results in a robust model with better performance compared with other ML approaches. The main contribution of this paper is the introduction of a tree-based IDS methodology that can accurately detect intrusions and identify 14 classes of attacks on VANET, such as Denial-of-Service (DoS), Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS), PortScan, and Botnet (Uma & Padmavathi, 2013), by using multiple ML algorithms.

The remaining sections of the paper are structured as follows. Table 1 reports the meaning of the abbreviation and acronyms used in this paper. The related works in VANET security are recalled

in Section 2. The IDS and type of attacks on VANET are described in Section 3, and the proposed model is presented in Section 4. Then, Sections 5 and 6 discuss the experiment, outcomes, and new directions in VANET security research. Section 7 concludes by summarizing the paper and future works.

Table 1. Acronyms used in the paper

Acronym	Description	Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence	ITS	Intelligent Transportation Systems
AV	Autonomous Vehicles	KNN	K-nearest neighbors
CAN	Controller Area Network	LSTM	Long short-term memory
DDoS	Distributed denial-of-service	ML	Machine Learning
DoS	Denial-of-service	RF	Random Forest
DT	Decision Tree	SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Oversampling Techniques
ECU	Electronic Control Unit	VANET	Vehicular ad hoc network
EV	Electric Vehicles	V2I	Infrastructure
ICT	Information Communications Technology	V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
IDS	Intrusion Detection Systems	V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
IoV	Internet of Vehicles	XGBoost	EXtreme Gradient Boosting
IoT	Internet of Things	EXT	Extra-trees classifier

2. Related work

Recent years have seen an increase in studies focusing on developing IDS for VANET and connected vehicles. Detecting cyberattacks on vehicular networks (V2V/V2I) is a hot topic in the academic community. Multi-cluster anomaly-based has been proposed by Sharma and Kaul (2018) to detect attacks in VANET. The Dolphin Swarm Algorithm optimizes the model, which can accurately identify the various forms of cyberattacks. The results were compared with many existing models in different parameters, such as detection rate, detection time, and alarm rate. They concluded that the proposed

multi-cluster model performs better on VANET than existing IDS. Alshammari et al. (2018) developed a classification framework to detect malicious attacks on internal vehicular networks with the help of hybrid algorithms, which are k-nearest neighbor (KNN) and support vector machine (SVM). The model is built based on KNN as a hybrid model with the support of SVM and utilizes the "DoS dataset" and the "fuzzy dataset" to simulate vehicle hacking. In order to effectively detect attacks on AVs' communication networks, Khan et al. (2021) presented an approach using a bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architecture based on deep learning (DL) in addition to the conventional state-based approach. The developed framework is tested using two benchmark datasets: UNSWNB-15 for communications with external networks and the car hacking dataset for in-vehicle communications. Ashraf et al. (2020) introduced DL-based IDS to identify suspicious network behavior in In-Vehicle Networks, V2V, and V2I networks. Two benchmark datasets were used to assess the proposed IDS: the car hacking dataset for internal communication and the UNSWNB15 dataset for external communication networks. Safi Ullah et al. (2022) introduced a DL framework to detect in-vehicles attacks and external intrusions on VANET. The suggested model relies on LSTM and the gated recurrent unit. The model's performance was examined on a combined DDoS dataset for external communication and a car-hacking dataset for internal. Bangui et al. (2022) presented a hybrid IDS approach for VANET to optimize the performance of IDSs by combining RF classifier and a posterior detection method based on coresets to enhance the detection accuracy. The most recent dataset, CICIDS2017, includes the cyberattack scenarios, such as the most common types of assaults in VANET, such as DoS Slowloris attacks and DDoS attacks. An anomaly-based IDS was proposed by Olufowobi et al. (2019) to detect Controller Area Network (CAN) attacks using the adaptive cumulative sum method. Based on the changes in statistical patterns, this method can efficiently identify intrusions with a minimal figure of delay. They tested how well the detection system worked by employing the CAN logs included in the Car-Hacking Dataset. A unique hybrid IDS was proposed by Yang et al. (2021), which accurately identifies the various forms of cyberattacks, including those launched on internal and external vehicular networks. The model was evaluated and tested on the CICIDS2017 and CAN-intrusion-dataset. An effective two-layer IDS mechanism for vehicular communication networks was introduced by Mirzaee et al. (2021), which makes use of collaborative detection between two IDSs located on the vehicle and at the network's edge. The proposed model was tested on a widely used CICIDS2017 dataset for IDS systems. To detect Bot attacks on Internet of Vehicles (IoV), Aswal et al. (2020) developed an ML model representing these attacks in a VANET system. Moreover, they did not include any other attacks from the CICIDS2017 dataset. Rosay et al.

(2020) presented a network IDS based on a multi-layer perceptron to identify cyberattacks on connected vehicles. The model has been evaluated on two versions of CICIDS2017 dataset and installed on a vehicle microprocessor.

This paper starts from the current research results and uses synergically tree-based ML techniques and a hybrid FS method to assist the model in selecting relevant and significant features from the dataset without duplicating data. By such choice, we accurately identify VANET intrusions and current assaults like DoS, DDoS, Ports can, and Bot by obtaining improved results with respect to the related literature.

3. IDS in VANET

In this section, we present the vulnerabilities of vehicular networks and the development of IDS against attacks.

3.1. Attacks on Vehicular Networks

There are two types of attacks on the current vehicular networks: internal and external.

3.1.1. Internal attacks

Currently, the primary defensive techniques against intrusions are firewalls, access control, and cryptography. These processes serve as the initial line of protection for connected vehicular networks. Cryptography provides secure communication, while access control was implemented for user authentication. However, the level of internal security that they provide to in-vehicle systems is insufficient. A CAN is a bus standard for EVs, and it has been exposed to several attacks due to its broadcasting approach, data encryption needs, and insecure priority mechanism (Gmiden et al., 2016). By inserting malicious messages into CAN packets, attackers may intrude on a system and have complete vehicle control in various ways, including gear and RPM spoofing. This type of assault is referred to a message injection attack and can result in legitimate nodes or vehicles. The most common kind of intra-vehicle assault is called a message injection attack (Liu, 2017).

3.1.2. External attacks

VANET is a wireless mobile network that facilitates communication between Roadside Units, V2I and V2V. The absence of firewalls and gateways in such wireless networks makes them vulnerable to attacks from anywhere within the radio range. Furthermore, unlike wired networks, an attacker does

not need physical access to the car to launch an attack. Each vehicle can be compromised since they are exposed, and the cars are permitted to travel autonomously without any protection from attack (Erritali & El Ouahidi, 2013). As external communication employs a decentralized design, self-driving cars depend on the cooperation of other vehicles inside their radio coverage region. In VANETs, systems security measures such as encryption/decryption processes and digital signatures may reduce the number of possible vulnerabilities, serving as the first line of defense. Nevertheless, self-driving cars need a second layer of protection to detect and even identify unknown attacks, which the current system's security techniques cannot avoid.

Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability, also known as the CIA triad, are highlighted as the three primary data and information security goals in any network, including VANET (Quentin Covert et al. 2020). Figure 1 reports the cyberattacks that can occur in VANET, divided into the different CIA attacks.

- **Attacks on Confidentiality:** This attack aims to breach the confidentiality of VANET and makes it possible for the attacker to listen to the conversation between nodes and try to steal the user credentials and other important information (Zhang et al., 2014).
- **Attacks on Integrity:** The attacker hacks the network without changing the message's content and adding delay, which makes the user get the message later than expected. Therefore, information and messages must be sent to VANET users at the right time because breaching the network integrity results in disasters (Raw et al., 2013).
- **Attacks on Availability:** To accomplish the primary objective of VANET, it must always be accessible to allow users access to all applications and services. However, its main purpose will be useless if users cannot communicate across the network (Sumra et al., 2015). These attacks are associated with network resources' accessibility, reliability, performance, and data processing. Network attacks have recently been a concern for many institutions that provide wired and wireless services, including government and private organizations. With the emergence of VANET and smart cars, there has been increased concern about these attacks, which may lead to tragic accidents and privacy breaches. Table 2 reports the common types of attacks on network availability.

Figure 1. Cyberattacks goals on VANET based on CIA triad.

Table 2. Common attacks on availability.

DoS	ADoS attack is an attempt to disable a computer system or network so its intended users cannot access it.
DDoS	A DDoS attack attempts to block a server, service, or network's traffic by overloading the target and its surrounding infrastructure with an enormous amount of Internet traffic.
PortScan	Attackers send packets to specified ports on a host and find vulnerabilities and determine which service versions are running.
Brute-Force	Attackers use trial and error to get login credentials by cracking passwords and encryption keys.
Botnet	Attackers hack many connected vehicles and network components with one or more bot viruses and use this swarm of infected systems to launch different attacks on the connected systems.
Blackhole	Attack on communication protocol where the malicious node attempt to decrease the availability of VANET and block vehicles' communication
Syble	The attacker takes over the network and the service's system by operating many active fake identities.
Infiltration	Attackers disconnect hacked network systems and malicious implant nodes for future attacks
GPS Spoofing	It is an attack on GPS where the attacker sends a wrong geographic location to the victim node.

4. The IDS Model

The proposed system is an IDS framework focused on protecting the external vehicular network and built to obtain optimal results such as high accuracy and detection rate. We present a multi-level IDS model to accurately classify normal and abnormal activities across VANET. The model is evaluated on well-known data benchmarks (CICIDS2017) containing recent attacks with 80 network flow features.

In the following section, we describe the system architecture in detail, including CICIDS2017 dataset, and explain the phases in the architecture of the proposed model.

4.1. The system architecture

In this section the architecture of the proposed IDS model is described in detail and depicted in Figure 2. The framework is divided into four main phases: data preparation, feature engineering, ML model and evaluation. The first phase implements data pre-processing techniques such as data sampling, normalization, and data imbalance solutions like Synthetic Minority Over Sampling Techniques (SMOTE) (Chawla et al., 2002). The data should be prepared in order to create a representative subset for training and testing, while avoiding outliers and class imbalance issues. The second phase implements feature selection techniques, i.e., RF and FCBF, that are used to remove unnecessary and redundant features, as well as low the dimensionality and noisy features that might affect the accuracy of the prediction result.

Then, in the ML classification third phase, the four tree-based ML methods are applied synchronously to detect unpredicted attacks and are combined by a stacking method to further improve the attacks detection accuracy. In the final phase, the attack prediction accuracy is evaluated by standard performance metrics like accuracy, recall, precision, and score. The aim is to detect whether an attack occurs or does not occur and consequently a corrective action is needed or not.

Figure 2. Multi-level IDS model architecture.

4.2. Dataset description

The CICIDS2017 benchmark is a simulation of network data from the real world. The dataset is created on an internet-connected testbed consisting of a network infrastructure hosting a wide variety of client devices and operating systems that simulate real-world scenarios. CICFlowmeter-V3.0 (Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity 2017) is applied to this dataset to extract features and labels, from which 80 network flow features have been extracted. The attacks in this dataset can break down into botnet, infiltration, brute force FTP/ SSH, DoS and DDoS attacks, heartbeat, and web, which are not found in any other datasets (Sharafaldin et al., 2018). Using the B-Profile system, CICIDS2017 abstractly profiles how people interact with each other and simulate different multi-stage attack scenarios. These datasets differ from others because they are based on real-world data generating from wireless local area networks (WLANs) and mobile networks and can be trusted. To ensure that the evaluation is accurate, the benchmarking uses 11 criteria, such as total traffic and available protocols (Pelletier & Abualkibash, 2020). However, there is a lack of availability of VANET datasets for evaluating external vehicular network IDS for many reasons, such as data privacy, distribution, and availability.

Despite that, WLANs and mobile networks are the communication techniques used in VANET. Therefore, all the attacks on such networks are similar to malicious intrusions executed on VANET. Since CICIDS2017 is the most comprehensive and illustrative available cyber-attack dataset, the proposed IDS uses such benchmark data to evaluate the model's efficiency in detecting attacks on

VANET. Furthermore, the types of attacks included in the CICIDS2017 dataset are reported in Table 2.

4.3. Data preprocessing

The first phase in the data analysis process is data pre-processing. Various techniques, data sampling, normalization, and data imbalance solutions are used in this phase as described in the following sections.

4.3.1. Normalization

Some of the features in an IDS available public dataset are nominal, while others are not normalized. Normalization of data is an essential pre-processing step for learners who learn from the statistical properties of features. Data normalization is the process of normalizing each attribute's value so that it falls within a specified range, preventing the influence of one attribute from dominating the effects of the others. Linear and non-linear techniques can be used to normalize feature-based data. In particular, Z-score normalization is used to normalize the numerical attributes between 0 and 1, minimize their values, and decrease the training processes (Fei et al., 2021):

$$Z = \frac{x-\mu}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

where Z stands for the Z-score normalization, σ refers to the standard deviation of features, x stands for the values, and μ the mean of the sample.

4.3.2. Data encoding

Since most of ML algorithms cannot work with string data type, the dataset is encoded using a label encoder. This encoder method helps to convert categorical features in the dataset into numerical features, which are accepted as input to the proposed ML model.

4.3.3. Data sampling

It is challenging to train ML models on enormous amounts of network data which requires repeatedly training an ML model. Data sampling is a standard ML approach that can create a portion of the original dataset to simplify the training phase and improve the performance of the model training process.

The proposed model for data-sampling uses the K-means-based algorithm to produce a high representative portion of the original data (10% of the dataset are used in the considered experiments). K-means seeks to find the optimal values for each of the distances between each data point and cluster's centroid by minimizing the sum of the squares of those distances (Hartigan & Wong, 1979):

$$J = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^n \|x_i^j - \mu_j\|^2 \quad (2)$$

where J is the objective function, k is the number of clusters, n is the number of cases, x_i^j is the data point of case i in cluster j and μ_j is centroid for cluster j . K-means is a widely used technique for sampling because of its simplicity and low computational requirements.

4.3.4. SMOTE

It is used to solve the class imbalance problem, in particular for oversampling. The oversampling issue occurs when the dataset classes are imbalanced in terms of samples. In this case, SMOTE is applied to solve the oversampling problem in order to balance the classes dimensions.

4.4. Feature Engineering

The main objective of feature engineering is to select the best features from the pre-processed dataset enhancing the accuracy of the IDS and helping to detect any vulnerable attacks on the vehicle network at low cost. Using feature selection techniques helps to decrease the cost of the ML workflow in terms of time and resource usage. Additionally, it enables feature transformation and the removal of unnecessary features to improve the quality and accuracy of results. Generally, the quality of datasets would be enhanced for more precise and effective model learning by choosing the ideal set of features. In this work, a double feature selection method is implemented before the training stage based on RF and FCBF. In particular, RF is well known as the best method to select features with high accuracy and faster results. Anyway, RF method gives the same importance level to the relevant features, leading to redundancy in the selected features. Hence, we use the FCBF method to filter the relevant features and remove the redundancy in the final set of selected features.

In the following, we describe in detail the RF and FCBF methods.

4.4.1. RF method

RF is an ensemble-learning method utilized for data classification and regression. The regression tree is a hierarchical arrangement of criteria or constraints gradually executed from the root to the tree's leaf. Trees are generated using chosen bootstrap samples and randomly picked n -estimator parameter in each node separation in the RF technique (Breiman, L. 2001). RF method delivers a unique validity and model interpretation estimate within ML approaches. In the first stage of feature selection, RF technique calculates the importance of a feature based on its ability to increase the pureness of the leaves, and selects the 38 features as shown in Table 3, and these features are fed to the second filtering method.

4.4.2 FCBF method

FCBF is used in addition to the RF method since RF method removes the insignificant features to manage and decreases the time complexity but does not avoid feature redundancy. Indeed, the model accuracy is not optimized as many redundant and unneeded features remain in the dataset after RF application. Additionally, the model's time and space complexity may rise due to feature redundancy. Therefore, reducing duplicated features and computing the input correlation characteristics might positively impact the model's efficiency. Moreover, the FCBF technique is applied as a second FS technique because it shows excellent performance, especially on high-dimensional datasets, by reducing time complexity and removing redundant features while preserving important features.

The first step in the FCBF process is to select a collection of features with a high degree of correlation with the FCBF class. After that, the resulting values are sorted into a list based on the feature importance. It uses heuristics to eliminate features that are not necessary and retain the features that are more important to the class. The proposed method selects the best 25 features in the dataset, as shown in Table 4, which directly impacts on the model accuracy.

Table 3. Selected features by RF

No	Features	NO	Features
1	SubflowFwd Bytes	20	Fwd IAT Min
2	Total Length of Fwd Packets	21	Flow IAT Max
3	Total Length of Bwd Packets	22	InitWinbytesforward
4	SubflowBwd Bytes	23	Avg Bwd Segment Size
5	Flow IAT Std	24	Bwd Packet Length Max
6	Bwd Packets/s	25	Destination Port
7	Fwd Packet Length Std	26	Bwd Packet Length Std
8	InitWinbytesbackward	27	SYN Flag Count
9	Fwd IAT Total	28	Max Packet Length
10	Bwd Packet Length Min	29	Flow IAT Min
11	Flow Duration	30	Fwd Packet Length Mean
12	Fwd Packet Length Max	31	Average Packet Size
13	Bwd IAT Total	32	Packet Length Variance
14	Fwd IAT Mean	33	min_seg_size_forward
15	Fwd Header Length.l	34	Packet Length Std
16	Fwd Header Length	35	Packet Length Mean

17	Flow IAT Mean	36	Active Min
18	Fwd IAT Std	37	Total Fwd Packets
19	Bwd Packet Length Mean	38	Bwd Header Length

Table 4. Selected features by FCBF

No	Features	NO	Features
1	Total Length of Fwd Packets	14	Flow IAT Mean
2	SubflowFwd Bytes	15	Flow IAT Std
3	Bwd Packet Length Std	16	Flow IAT Max
4	Fwd IAT Std	17	Max Packet Length
5	Fwd IAT Min	18	Destination Port
6	Bwd Packets/s	19	Fwd Packet Length Std
7	Avg Bwd Segment Size	20	Fwd Header Length.l
8	Bwd Packet Length Mean	21	Total Length of Bwd Packets
9	Init_Win_bytes_backward	22	Fwd Header Length
10	Packet Length Std	23	Bwd Packet Length Max
11	Init_Win_bytes_forward	24	Flow Duration
12	Fwd IAT Total	25	min_seg_size_forward
13	Flow IAT Min		-

4.5. The ML model

According to Intel Corporation (2016), four terabytes of data are generated daily due to the necessary technological improvement of connected vehicles. Strong IDS based on ML is often suggested to achieve vehicle security related to road and human life safety, protecting vehicular network communications. In this phase, we aim to examine the considered pre-processed dataset to detect the attacks by classifying the traffic as normal and abnormal. For that goal, we implement a multi-ML algorithms model consisting of four tree-based algorithms to detect unpredicted attacks, achieve accurate results. The proposed tree-based algorithms are XGBoost, RF, DT, and EXT classifiers.

The DT algorithm is a typical ML technique that fits data into a tree structure in order to generate predictions. The depth of the tree, minimum weight, full sample nodes, minimum sample split, fraction leaf, and minimum sample leaf are some of the DT hyper-parameters that need to be tuned. The DT is the foundation of all the tree-based algorithms, designed to increase model processing speed through parallelization. In addition, XGBoost provides a good balance between performance and

computational complexity. RF is also used for classification and it is a tree-based algorithm that utilizes the majority voting rule to merge many different DT classifiers.

On the other hand, EXT method combines several randomized decision trees that have been constructed using various subsets of a dataset. The reason behind selecting tree-based algorithms is that they make it possible to execute many tasks simultaneously, which notably minimizes the time required for model training and improves its performance. Moreover, a tree-based algorithm determines the significance of features during the training phase. Since traffic data on the vehicular network is non-linear, tree-based algorithms are the best choice to deal with it. Finally, in the process of ensemble development, tree-based algorithms use the randomization to encourage the development of a flexible ensemble model with higher generalizability on various domains compared to existing ML approaches.

It is also important to optimize the parameters of each tree-based algorithm to avoid the use of default parameter values. To this purpose, we apply HPO method in this work to select the best hyper-parameter configuration in each model. In addition, the stacking technique is used to ensemble the four tree-based algorithms. This technique is an ensemble ML method aiming at learning how to combine the predictions at best from several well-performing ML models (Snoek et al., 2012).

The Bayesian Optimization (BO) (Bergstra et al. 2011) technique is applied with the Tree Parzen Estimator (TPE) (Dewancker et al., 2016) in this phase. The BO is an iterative method frequently adopted for supporting HPO process. In particular, BO is used in ML to tune the hyper-parameters of a given model with good performance, on a validation dataset.

The Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) is a sequential model-based optimization approach. These methods sequentially construct models to approximate the performance of hyper-parameters based on historical measures, and then consequently find new hyper-parameters to evaluate.

In order to use TPE, the observation results are first separated into excellent and bad results using a pre-defined percentile y . Then the two different sets of results are modeled using basic Parzen windows:

$$p(x | y, D) = \begin{cases} l(x), & \text{if } y < y^* \\ g(x), & \text{if } y > y^* \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In (3) y^* is the threshold value of the objective function, x is the proposed set of hyperparameters, y is the actual value of the objective function using hyperparameters x , and $p(y | x)$ is the conditioned probability expressing the probability of y given x . In addition, $g(x)$ and $l(x)$ represent probability of identifying hyper-parameters in areas that have performed well and areas that have performed poorly, respectively. By increasing the ratio $l(x)/g(x)$, BO-TPE can determine the ideal values for the hyper-

parameters. The complexity of BO-TPE in terms of time is $O(n \log n)$, which is less than what the other methods require.

In conclusion, the proposed IDS model training process could be performed on an external server machine on VANET with high performance and computational speed. The model can also minimize the latency and fulfill the vehicle system's real-time requirements. The implemented Multi-level IDS Tree-based model that integrates feature selection technologies, ML algorithms, HPO-BO optimization and stacking process, allows optimizing the detection rate of attacks on VANET, by outperforming existing approaches.

4.6. Evaluation methods

During the evaluation of an IDS, the detection rate, as well as the false-positive rate, are important criteria that should be taken into consideration. Many different measures may be utilized for IDS performance evaluation. We use standard evaluation metrics, as described in Table 5, like accuracy, recall, precision, and f-score to evaluate performance of the proposed model (Goutte & Gaussier, 2005).

Table 5. Confusion and evaluation measures

ConfusionMatrix (CM)	Prediction	
	Intrusion	Legitimate
	Actual Intrusion	TP
	legitimate	FN
		FP
		TN

Accuracy (Acc)	The percentage of correctly predicted instances in the testing dataset	$Acc = \frac{TP+TN}{(TP+TN + FP+FN)} (4)$
Precision	The number of true positives divided by the total of true positives and false positives	$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} (5)$
Recall	The number of true positives divided by the total of true positives and false negatives	$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} (6)$
<i>F-score</i>	The harmonic average eof recall and precision knew	$FM = 2 \times \frac{precision \times recall}{precision + recall} (7)$

In order to determine the intrusion detection accuracy of the proposed model, we use the confusion matrix. The confusion matrix approach is typically applied when dealing with classification issues since it accurately depicts the target class and predicates the desired class result. It calculates the pairwise likeness between every set of classes using several similarity metrics. The confusion matrix has four alarms rate that have to be calculated during the evaluation process, providing the value of the evaluation metrics:

$$\text{True positive rate } TPR = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{True negative rate } TNR = 1 - FPR \quad (9)$$

$$\text{False positive rate } FPR = \frac{FP}{TN + FP} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{False negative rate } FNR = 1 - TPR \quad (11)$$

where TP is the number of intrusions correctly detected, TN is the number of non-intrusions correctly detected, FP is the number of non-intrusions incorrectly detected, and FN is the number of intrusions incorrectly detected.

5. Experimental setup and results

5.1. Experimental Setup

The model is developed in the Jupyter environment (Pimentel et al., 2021) and uses Python and its libraries which support feature engineering, ML, and HPO, such as Pandas, Xgboost, Hyperopt, and Scikit-learn. The experiments are carried out on a Toshiba Satellite Pro with Core i5-1135G7 (CPU) (4.20 GHz) and 16GB of memory 3200MHz, Intel Iris Xe Graphics 8GB, and Windows 10 Home 64Bit. The experiment takes approximately 200 hours (around 9 days) and the model is run in different cases. At first, we download the dataset from the Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity website (2017), the version for ML, which is in the form of a CS file in a compressed size of about 1GB. The data are divided into 8 CSV files; each file is generated on a different day and with different type of attacks. We combined these files into one file so that the model reads the data from one file, which is the best way to save time and reduce effort on the processor, reading from one source.

Then, a normalization process is performed for the data using Z-score. Data sampling is done using the K-mean technique, where the algorithm chooses the best 10% of the data with a size of 100 megabytes, representing the entire dataset. Successively, we apply feature selection methods: the first RF method selects 38 features, and then the second FCBF method selects 25 features. We run the model with seven different number of features: 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, and 38. We find that when selecting 25 features, the accuracy and evaluation metrics results are the best, as shown in Table 6. Figure 3 shows the results obtained testing the IDS model with different features.

Table 6. Model evaluation with a different number of features in CICIDS2017 dataset

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Sore
10 features	0.9959	0.9973	0.9967	0.9964
15 features	0.9962	0.9974	0.9969	0.9965
20 features	0.9967	0.9978	0.9971	0.9968
25 features	0.99856	0.99849	0.9985	0.99851
30 features	0.9981	0.9982	0.9977	0.9978
35 features	0.9980	0.9981	0.9979	0.9980
38 features	0.9975	0.9979	0.9976	0.99768

Figure 3. Feature selected performance with evaluation matrices.

We also noticed an imbalance in the classes, so the use of SMOTE is needed to solve the class imbalance issue. It works by generating synthetic samples for minority categories and avoiding bias in the ML model (Chawla et al., 2002).

In the proposed ML model, each tree-based algorithm is executed in three cases: 1) without the feature selection, 2) with the feature selection but without the optimization algorithm HPO, and 3) using feature selection techniques and HPO algorithms. It is noticed that when FS and HPO are used, the model can detect intrusions with higher accuracy of up to 98.86%, as shown in Table 7, which

outperforms the results obtained by other researchers working on the same dataset, applying various techniques, as shown in Table 8. Moreover, Figure 4 shows the results obtained by the proposed model with various matrices of evaluation.

Table 7. Model evaluation results in three different cases.

Evaluation	Accuracy			Precision			Recall			F1-score		
	Without FS	Without HPO	With HPO	Without FS	Without HPO	With HPO	Without FS	Without HPO	With HPO	Without FS	Without HPO	With HPO
XGBoost	0.9963	0.9966	0.99830	0.9967	0.9975	0.99834	0.9963	0.9966	0.9983	0.9964	0.9969	0.9983
RF	0.9977	0.99855	0.99844	0.9981	0.99856	0.9985	0.9978	0.99855	0.9984	0.9979	0.9985	0.9984
DT	0.9972	0.99731	0.99773	0.9975	0.99739	0.99782	0.9973	0.99731	0.9977	0.9974	0.9973	0.9977
EXT	0.9968	0.99809	0.99848	0.9972	0.99810	0.99848	0.9977	0.99809	0.9984	0.9969	0.9980	0.9984
Stack of all (XGBoost,RF,DT, EXT)	0.9980	0.9983	0.99856	0.9982	0.9983	0.99849	0.9980	0.9983	0.9985	0.9981	0.9982	0.9985

Figure 4. Performance of model on CICIDS2017 with different evaluation matrices

Table8. Comparison between our work and literature.

Paper	Dataset	Security threats	ML algorithm	Detection result
Alshammari et al.	car-hacking datasets CHD	DoS and Fuzzy attacks	KNN and SVM	Ac: 96 F1: 93
Izhar khan et al	UNSWNB-15 + CHD	DoS, zero-day, Reconnaissance and injections attacks, Gear spoofing, RPM spoofing, and Fuzzy attacks.	PCA -bidirectional LSTM	Ac: 99.11 Pr: 99.13 Re: 98.42 Fs: 99.09 Kp: 98.22
Javed Ashraf et al.	UNSWNB-15 + CHD	DoS, zero-day, Reconnaissance and injections attacks, Gear spoofing, RPM spoofing, and Fuzzy attacks.	LSTM Autoencoder	Ac: 99 F1: 99
Safi Ullah et al.	CIC DoS CICIDS 2017 CSE-CIC-IDS 2018 CHD	DDoS, fuzzing, and spoofing	(LSTM) and gated recurrent unit extra tree classifier (ETC) for FS SMOTE stratified random sampling (SRS)	Ac:99.5%
Bangui et al.	CICIDS 2017	DDoS, DoS, Heartbleed, PortScan,Bot,FTP-Patator, SSH-Patator, Web Attack, Infiltration	- Random forest - Bisecting k-means - Weighted K-means - Coresets	Ac: 96.93 F1: 94.41 Pr: 98.5 Re: 90.4
Olufowobi et al.	Car-Hacking Dataset	DoS, Fuzzy Attack, Spoofing Attack	cumulative sum change-point detection algorithm	Ac: 96
Rosay et al.	CICIDS 2017	DDoS, DoS, Heartbleed, PortScan,Bot,FTP-Patator, SSH-Patator, Web Attack, Infiltration	Multi-Layer Perceptron	Ac: 99
Proposed model	CICIDS 2017	DoS Hulk ·PortScan ·DDoS ·DoS GoldenEye ·FTP-Patator ·SSH-Patator ·DoS slowloris ·DoS Slowhttptest ·Bot ·Web Attack Brute Force ·Web Attack XSS ·Infiltration ·Web Attack SQL Injection ·Heartbleed.	Multi-level Tree-based (DT, RF, XGBoost,EXT), BO-TPE.	Ac: 99.86 Pr: 0.99849 Re: 0.9985. F1: 0.99851

5.2. Result Discussion

The proposed IDS model shows its effectiveness in predicting different kind of attacks on VANET. It is based on different strategic levels: 1) data processing is applied to purify the initial dataset from errors and missing data; 2) feature selection is necessary to choose the features that can improve the accuracy of detecting intrusions; 3) ML algorithms are applied to discover gaps by classifying the normal and the abnormal traffic based on the classes available in the dataset; 4) evaluate the prediction accuracy by using standard metrics. Although this field has received the attention of many researchers and several research works have been submitted in this context, rarely it can be found a hybrid IDS framework that obtained such a high prediction accuracy. Using two methods to filter the features led

to selecting the important features that help the model deal with a real dataset containing data similar to the real-time data. Tree-based ML algorithms are used since they work perfectly on non-linear data and can perform many tasks simultaneously, which is needed during the training process. In addition, tree-based models use randomness during the building process, which helps to construct a flexible model that can be generalized to any domain case in the future. We train the model for 200 hours, with an amount of 10% of the original data. The data are divided into 80% for training and 20% for examination. Although the training time is long due to the size of the data used, which is 100 MB, the results are more accurate and show their effectiveness on the real-time systems of the VANET. The CICIDS2017 dataset used is recently updated and has been used for IDS by many researchers, and this is because of the reliability of the data and is also comprehensive for most modern attacks. There is the need to secure EVs networks, for internal or external communication, and the development of such systems is essential in the future of smart cars. Correct information may save lives and prevent disasters, while lacking data or giving the wrong position may cause unfortunate accidents.

6. Conclusion

This paper introduces a new Multi-level Tree-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) using machine learning (ML) algorithms and tests its ability to identify 14 classes of attacks. To ensure the quality of the input data, we used two feature selection techniques in the model. We developed a multi-level ML technique using four tree-based algorithms (DT, RF, XGBoost, and EXT). The model includes an optimization layer where bayesian optimization BO-TPE is implemented in each method to further improve accuracy and detection rate. The proposed model was evaluated using CICIDS2017 dataset, and the model can detect different attacks effectively on VANET with an accuracy of 99.86%. The experimental findings on the vehicular network demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed solution and the accuracy in intrusion detection.

In future work, we plan to develop a comprehensive IDS framework that detects and classifies intrusions in the internal and external vehicle networks so that it prevents such attacks at the in-vehicle level or at the VANET level. We also plan to expand the computing resources to develop the model and make it work on a larger size of data, which may reach 90% of the original data size. Moreover, we will simulate VANET on well-known simulation programs to produce data for a specific geographic area and implement the model on realistic environment.

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